

Classifying LIDAR Points by Filtered Elevation Value: Reclassifying LIDAR Points by Selecting a Specified Elevation Range

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Keywords:

LIDAR, LAS classifications, GIS, Reclassifying Points, Selection by Elevation Range, Filtered Elevation Values;

Reclassifying LiDAR Points by selecting a specified elevation range involves filtering and reorganizing LiDAR data based on their elevation values. This process allows users to select points within a defined elevation range or to exclude unwanted points, such as noise or outliers that don't meet the desired criteria.

Once filtered, the selected points are reclassified into different ASPRS categories, grouping them by elevation. For instance, points can be categorized into ranges that represent terrain features like ground, water, low vegetation, high vegetation, or other relevant landscape elements. This improves data accuracy and clarity for further analysis.

To begin this process in SGIS v.R, we've already loaded two LAS files. We'll walk through the procedure step by step, starting with activating the Selection tool.

Fig.1 Two LAS files have been preloaded into SGIS v.R, and the process begins by activating the 'Selection' function.

In our example, the LAS data depicts an island surrounded by water. Since the file is still undergoing quality control, the points representing water are currently classified as ground points.

To address this, we need to efficiently select all water points and reclassify them to class 9, which corresponds to water according to the ASPRS classification system.

We'll use the 'Selection By Elevation Range' tool for this task.

However, before proceeding, we first need to assess the elevation values in the area. To do this, we'll activate the 'Selection' function. By simply clicking on the ground (which will later be reclassified as water), we can begin the process.

Without zooming in, we can select multiple points at once with a single click from the zoomed-out view. The software will then highlight the selected points in red.

The red highlighting is a customizable setting, which in this case, we've chosen as the default highlight color.

Fig.2 Activating the 'Selection' function and clicking on the ground area (to be reclassified as water), we select multiple points from a zoomed-out view. The selected points are highlighted in red, indicating they are ready for further processing.

By pressing CTRL+S, the Layer Statistics dialog will open.

On the second tab, labeled "Details," you'll find the coordinates for the selected group of points, including the X, Y, and Z values.

If you scroll to the bottom of the list, you'll also see the minH and maxH values, which represent the minimum and maximum elevation values for the selected points.

Fig.3 Pressing CTRL+S opens the Layer Statistics dialog.

Fig.4 Scrolling to the bottom of the "Details" list reveals the minH and maxH values, representing the minimum and maximum elevation for the selected points.

In this case, we can see that the minH is 42.654m, and the maxH is 42.979m.

Next, we'll navigate to the Selection menu in the main ribbon and choose the 'Select Elements By Elevation Range' option. Then, we click on it to proceed.

Fig.5 Navigating to the Selection menu in the main ribbon and selecting the 'Select Elements By Elevation Range' option to proceed with the elevation-based selection process.

As soon as we click on the option, a dialog window appears, prompting users to select from three available options:

- We can check the first box to select points with an 'Elevation less than...' a specified value,
- The second box for 'Elevation greater than...' a given value, or
- The third option, 'Elevation Between...' for a range of values.

Since we already have both a minimum and maximum value, we'll use these to input the elevation range.

Above the input fields, there's a display bar that initially appears fully colored when the window opens, indicating that no filtering has been applied yet and all points from the active LAS layer are included.

After inputting our values from the example and pressing Enter, we immediately see the display bar adjust, showing that only a smaller subset of points falls within the selected elevation range.

Fig.6 The display bar starts fully colored, indicating no filtering. We input the minimum and maximum elevation values to set the range.

Fig.7 The display bar shows a reduced subset of points within the selected elevation range.

Next, we click on 'Select.' Once done, all points within the specified elevation range will be highlighted in the Graphics panel. We can now see that the ground points, which should be reclassified as water, have been accurately selected.

Fig.8 After clicking 'Select,' the points within the specified elevation range are highlighted in the Graphics panel, showing that the ground points to be reclassified as water have been accurately selected.

Fig.9 To organize and reclassify the selected points, we need to open the 'LIDAR' toolbox.

Next, we open the 'LIDAR' toolbox.

The selected points will stay highlighted unless we click 'Clear Selection.' First, we click on 'Existing' to display the current classification codes in the memo box, showing classes 1-7. To make things clearer, we click 'Uncheck' to deselect any empty classifications. Once it's organized, we find and check the box for the Water classification. At this point, we can also choose a specific color to represent the water points.

Fig.10 To reclassify the selected points as Water, we check the corresponding checkbox. Although the class already has a preset color, we'll adjust it slightly to demonstrate the customization options available in SGIS v.R.

Fig.11 After finalizing the settings, we click 'Set Up' to complete the point reclassification.

Once the settings are finalized, we click 'Set Up' to reclassify the points. All selected points are instantly reclassified into classification number 9, adopting the assigned color for that class.

The changes are reflected immediately in the graphics panel.

Fig.12 The reclassified points are instantly updated and displayed in the graphics panel.

The previously ground-classified points have now been reclassified as water. Since this process was applied only to the first LAS file, we'll repeat the same steps for the second file. Once the procedure is complete, and the water points are reclassified in both LAS files, we can select either file and, within the 'LIDAR' toolbox, click on 'Existing'. At this point, classifications 1-7, along with class 9 (representing water), will appear in the memo list box.

Fig.13 After reclassifying both LAS files, class 9 (Water) appears alongside classes 1-7 in the 'Existing' memo list.

To wrap up, we can add a Tile basemap to enhance visualization and clarity. This completes the procedure.

Fig.14 The procedure is complete.